

Comparison of foundation by Direct Shear Test in Different soil condition and its applicability in the context of Nepal.

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Abstract

In this paper, we mainly focused on the comparison of foundation in two different locations. Size of foundation depends on bearing capacity of soil. Standard proctor test has been conducted to determine Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) of soil and Direct shear test has been conducted to determine the shear strength parameters in OMC. Bearing capacity of soil is calculated from shear strength parameters using terzaghi's equation. Area of foundation is calculated and it is found that area differ by 34.47% at two locations.

Keywords: Foundation, direct shear test, shear strength parameters, bearing capacity.

1. Introduction

A. Background

i. Foundation

Foundation is a part of a structural system that supports the superstructure of a building and transmits its loads directly to the earth. Foundation design involves the study of both structural system and characteristics of supporting ground. It plays a crucial role in ensuring the stability, safety, and longevity of a structure by distributing its weight evenly and preventing settlement or movement caused by soil instability or subsidence.

ii. Bearing capacity

Bearing capacity is the capacity of soil to support the load that are applied on it. There are different methods to calculate bearing capacity of soil from Plate bearing test, Standard penetration test, Terzaghi's Bearing Capacity Theory, Cone Penetration Test, Vane shear test, Direct Shear test etc. In our context we have used Direct shear test to calculate bearing capacity.

Scope of research

The outcome of this research help in the following context of the foundation design.

- i. Foundation size varies based on soil characteristics; even minor changes can necessitate adjustments.

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- ii. For small and less significant projects, determining bearing capacity doesn't always require extensive field tests.
- iii. Simplified methods can be employed to assess bearing capacity for minor projects.
- iv. These methods help save time and resources by avoiding elaborate field testing procedures.

Objectives

The major objective of this project is to compare foundation by direct shear test in different soil location. This will finally give information that the size of foundation differs for minor change in soil characteristics and for small and less important work bearing capacity can be found easily without performing any heavy field test.

Limitations

- i. The research outcomes may be specific to the chosen topographic scenarios and site location.
- ii. All other factors affecting loading condition is kept constant. The only variable for foundation design and comparison is "different soil conditions.
- iii. This geotechnical report is based on the data collected from the two pits and from laboratory results and judgement of the author based on the experience.

2. Literature review

Soil moisture content plays a crucial role in determining bearing capacity, with saturated soils exhibiting lower bearing capacities due to reduced effective stress. Studies have investigated the relationship between soil moisture content and bearing capacity under different conditions. (1)

Terzaghi's seminal work in the 1940s laid the foundation for understanding soil bearing capacity. His theory proposed that bearing capacity depends on the soil's shear strength parameters and is influenced by factors such as the depth of the foundation and the shape of the footing. (2)

Several studies have explored the relationship between soil type and bearing capacity. Dense granular soils typically exhibit higher bearing capacities compared to cohesive soils due to their higher shear strength. (3)

Isolated footing is preferred in rocky soil. For gravel and sandy soil combined footing and strap footing is provided. Mat foundation is provided for hard clay. In soft clay having low bearing capacity pile foundation is used. In water logged area pile foundation is used. (4)

Pure clay would have a value of 0° and ϕ would rise with increasing sand content and density to approximately 40° for a compact sandy loam soil. Loose sands range between 25 to 30° . As pure clays are rarely found in top soils the typical value for a 'clay' soil would be in the range 5 to 10° . (5)

Soil properties such as cohesion, friction angle, permeability, and compressibility significantly influence the choice and design of foundations. The soil's bearing capacity, which is its ability to support the applied loads without failure, is a critical parameter in foundation design. (6)

3. Sample Collection, Preparation and Testing

i. Sample Collection

Sample is collected at two different locations of Lalitpur and Dhulikhel. Coordinate of lalitpur is 27°38'12"N 85°20'12"E and that of dhulikhel is 27°36'56"N 85°32'32"E. Representative soil sample is extracted by using hand sampling method at depth of 40-50cm from ground surface.

ii. Preparation and testing

- a) Standard proctor test is carried out as per the Indian Standard (IS: 2720 Part VII – 1980).
- b) Direct shear test is carried out at OMC according to IS 2720-13: Methods of test for soils, Part 13: Direct shear test.

Standard Proctor Test

Standard proctor test is conducted to determine the optimum moisture content of soil.

Table 1 Standard Proctor test for OMC

Test Name : Standard Proctor Test	Harsiddhi, Lalitpur.					Harsiddhi, Lalitpur.				
Observations	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
Wt. of mould + compacted soil (kg)	6.408	6.408	6.408	6.408	6.408	6.408	6.408	6.408	6.408	6.448
Wt. of empty mould (kg)	4.634	4.634	4.634	4.634	4.634	4.676	4.676	4.676	4.676	4.676
Wt of compacted soil (kg)	1.774	1.874	1.910	1.806	1.782	1.719	1.824	1.848	1.798	1.772
Volume of mould (m ³)	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
Wet density (kg/m ³)	1774	1874	1910	1806	1782	1719	1824	1848	1798	1772
Wt of empty container (kg)	0.039	0.047	0.051	0.040	0.046	0.042	0.046	0.040	0.049	0.047
Wt of container + wet soil (kg)	0.109	0.112	0.182	0.239	0.231	0.145	0.111	0.091	0.156	0.220
Wt of container + dry soil (kg)	0.018	0.022	0.026	0.032	0.035	0.024	0.029	0.032	0.034	0.037
Moisture content (%)	18.136	21.501	26.463	32.194	35.219	23.718	28.898	31.682	33.772	37.391
Dry density (kg/m ³)	1501.664	1542.369	1510.318	1366.176	1317.862	1389.455	1415.076	1403.382	1344.079	1289.747

Figure 1: Moisture Density Curve

DIRECT SHEAR TEST

The direct shear test is a laboratory method used to determine the shear strength parameters of soil specimens. shear strength parameters, cohesion (c) and angle of internal friction (ϕ). Normal stress is applied at 0.5kg/cm²

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1kg/cm² and 1.5kg/cm² and strain rate is applied at 1.25mm per minute.

Figure 2: Direct Shear Test Results

Table 2: Shear strength parameters from Direct Shear Test

		Dhulikhel	Lalitpur
SL.No	Max. Normal Stress (Kg/m ²)	Max. Shear Stress (Kg/m ²)	Max. Shear Stress (Kg/m ²)
1	5000.00	3800	2600
2	10000.00	4300	3100
3	15000.00	5100	3800
Results From Graph			
1	Angle of Internal Friction ⁰	7.41	6.843
2	Cohesion C Kg/m ²	3100.000	1966.7

Calculation of Bearing capacity.

The bearing capacity of soil is calculated using the Terzaghi's formula: $q_f = c'N_c + \gamma DN\gamma + 0.5\gamma BN\gamma$. Here, q_f is the ultimate bearing capacity, c' is the cohesion of soil, N_c , N_q , and $N\gamma$ are bearing capacity factors, D is the depth of footing, and γ is the unit weight of soil.

As from ϕ value criteria and from density of soil it is predicted that a general shear failure is possible. Hence, bearing capacity factors for general shear failure are as follow,

Table 3: Terzaghi's Equation Parameters

Parameters	Lalitpur	Dhulikhel
Φ	6.84	7.410
N_c	8.146	8.4086
N_q	2.005	2.1302
N_γ	0.758	0.8374
Sc	1.1	1
S_γ	0.9	0.9
(Take) Shape Factor (B/L)	0.5	0.5
unit wt. of soil (KN/m ²)	15.107	13.911
(Take) Structural loading (p KN)	76449.25	76449.25

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Depth of footing is taken as 1.5m.

Table 4 : Calculation of bearing capacity by Trial-and-Error method

S.N.	Initial qu (KN/m ²)	Area (m ²) =p/qu	Breadth (m) Bf=v(A*S.F)	qu by Terzaghi (KN/m ²)
Lalitpur				
1	150.00	509.662	15.963	300.564
2	300.56	254.353	11.277	276.428
3	276.43	276.561	11.759	278.911
4	278.91	274.099	11.707	278.641
5	278.64	274.365	11.712	278.670
6	278.67	274.336	11.712	278.667
7	278.67	274.339	11.712	278.667
Dhulikhel				
1	150.000	509.662	15.963	409.413
2	409.413	186.729	9.663	376.384
3	376.384	203.115	10.078	378.560
4	378.560	201.948	10.049	378.408
5	378.408	202.029	10.051	378.418
6	378.418	202.023	10.050	378.418
7	378.418	202.024	10.050	378.418

FOUNDATION COMPARISON

Table 5: Foundation Comparison of Lalitpur and Dhulikhel

Features	Lalitpur	Dhulikhel
Moisture Content (%)	21.5	29.5
Dry Density(g/cc)	1.54	1.418
Angle of Internal Friction(°)	6.84	7.41
Cohesion (Kg/cm ²)	0.197	0.310
Ultimate Bearing Capacity (KN/m ²)	278.667	378.418
Factor of Safety	3	3
Safe Bearing Capacity (KN/m ²)	92.88	126.14
Area of Foundation(m ²)	1016.632	666.130

Area of foundation required for Dhulikhel is 34.47% less than that of Lalitpur.

Bearing Capacity check from secondary sources.

Calculated bearing capacity of Dhulikhel ward no 6 is 126.14 KN/m² and bearing capacity obtained from secondary source is 126.53 KN/m². Hence calculated bearing capacity is within 0.3% difference range than that of secondary source. (7)

Conclusion

In this article we studied about the shear strength parameter of soil for calculating bearing capacity using Terzaghi's equation and effect of bearing capacity on foundation design in two different locations. We have observed following outcomes in our experiment.

- i. Bearing capacity of Dhulikhel sample is found higher than Lalitpur soil sample.
- ii. Approximate Bearing capacity can be calculated by the use of shear strength parameter obtained from direct shear test as it lies in range of bearing capacity obtained from other cumbersome field tests.
- iii. For the same structural loading, foundation area requirement for dhulikhel sample is found 34.47 % less than that of harsiddhi, Lalitpur soil sample. Which is directly associated with construction cost of foundation.
- iv. Direct shear test can be used as alternative for determining bearing capacity of a small and less significant project. As for small works where bearing capacity is unknown, this method can give overview for approximate foundation design for structural integrity in the context of rural areas of Nepal.

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